

STUDY ON THE FERRIC IRON ADSORPTION FROM ACID MINE DRAINAGE ON LEWATIT RESIN IN A FIXED-BED COLUMN

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ABSTRACT. The study aimed to determine the effect of the acid mine drainages' flow rate on the iron adsorption by ion-exchange resin LEWATIT MonoPlus TP 207 in a fixed-bed column and to evaluate which widely used models describe that process better. The ferrous iron was preliminary chemically oxidised by H_2O_2 and Na_2CO_3 addition and increased pH to 3.50 combined with the solution purging with air. After assembling fixed-bed columns, their bed volume (BV) was determined. The treated mining solution was delivered to fixed-bed columns by a peristaltic pump at 2.0, 3.0, and 4.0 BV flow rates. The iron adsorption efficiency on the LEWATIT resin was studied depending on the applied flow rate and the volume being treated. The experimental data obtained were modelled using the Bohart-Adams, Thomas, Yoon-Nelson, and Clark models. The results showed that at constant experimental conditions (temperature, ferric iron concentration, and pH), the applied flow rate had a significant effect on the parameters which are important from a practical (efficiency of iron removal, (Y); equilibrium iron and equilibrium copper contents of the resin, (q_{eq})) and a theoretical point of view (rate constants (k_{BA} , k_{TN} , k_{YN} , r); time of breakthrough (τ)). The Yoon-Nelson and Clark models were the models that best fitted the experimental results.

Keywords: iron, LEWATIT, adsorption, a fixed-bed column

Introduction

The hydrometallurgical processing of non-ferrous metals from raw materials usually relies on their leaching at a highly acidic pH, combined with the co-dissolution of a significant amount of iron. For that reason, iron removal is an obligatory preliminary step in the treatment/ processing of wastewater and laden leach solution from mining and metallurgical industries. Solvent extraction and ion exchange are the processes, and they are applied in two consecutive stages. The first stage is the selective removal of ferric iron and its concentration on the reagent surface. The organo-phosphorous acids are the main class of organic compounds used in solvent extraction. Their advantage is the selective extraction and a strong bond formation with ferric iron from the leach liquor (Azizorghaben et al., 2016). An approach similar to the above-mentioned is based on the operation of ion-exchange resins. They are prepared from a wide range of synthetic polymers, and each class is characterised by a specific surface group and a magnitude of surface charge. Therefore, it determines the resins' ability to extract selectively alkaline earth elements, non-ferrous metals or precious metals even from solutions with higher inorganic or organic compounds with excellent complexing properties. For that reason, the ion exchange resins are used not only for the processing of mining effluents and laden leach liquor from metallurgy (McKevitt and Dreisinger, 2009) but also for the final purification as a step in the secondary treatment of wastewater from the food industry (Victor-Ortega et al., 2016). LEWATIT ion exchange resins are commercial products widely used in practice for dealkalisation, softening, demineralisation of natural and industrial waters, catalysis and processing of different organic compounds to produce foods or biodiesel (Product Guide, 2021). Another study showed that the loading capacity of LEWATIT ion exchange resin to iron is equal to or higher than that of other ion-exchange resins applied at an industrial scale (McKevitt and Dreisinger, 2009).

The second stage of the laden leach liquors processing is the regeneration of the relevant active surface, and it is

achieved in the presence of a suitable inorganic acid. As a result, the extracted and concentrated amount of ferric iron is desorbed in a solution with higher purity and a volume considerably lower than the initial volume of the laden leach liquor (Azizorghaben et al., 2016). It enables further iron precipitation of hematite or magnetite with higher chemical purity, peculiar particle size, shape, surface, optical and magnetic properties which make them applicable in various industrial fields (Kulkarni et al., 2014).

The study aimed to determine the effect of the acid mine drainages' flow rate on the iron adsorption by LEWATIT MonoPlus TP 207 in a fixed-bed column and to evaluate which widely used models describe that process better.

Materials and methods

Acid mine drainage (AMD) from an abandoned copper mine in Northwest Bulgaria with acidic pH (2.26) was collected and analysed. The iron, copper, and zinc content was 3345, 137, and 311 mg/ L, respectively. The value of Eh shows that a significant part of the dissolved iron was a ferrous ion (Georgiev et al., 2021).

The experiments about the iron adsorption from acid mine drainage were carried out in fixed-bed columns with a total length of 10 cm. The experimental set-up consisted of a feed vessel (1), a peristaltic pump (2), a fixed-bed column (3), and a vessel collecting treated solutions (4) (Figure 1). In each fixed-bed column, two zones are distinguished – an adsorption and a supporting zone. The adsorption zone occupied the central part of the column, and it consisted of LEWATIT MonoPlus TP 207 ion-exchange resin (mean bead size 0.61 (\pm 0.05) mm). The supporting zones, situated in each column's inlet and outlet point, consisted of glass wool. The working volume of the adsorption zone, the so-called bed volume (BV), was determined by an upward injection of water at a rate of 0.048 m³/ h; till all pores existing between the resin's beans filled up with water. Initially, the ion exchange resin in a fixed bed column was activated with an upward injection of 0.1 L solution containing 100 g/ L sulphuric acid by a peristaltic pump at

0.096 L/h (Table 1). After that, the resin was washed with 0.240 L tap water at the same injection rate to extract the non-consumed acid from the exchange resin.

The ferrous iron in the collected AMD oxidised chemically in advance by H_2O_2 and Na_2CO_3 addition to pH 3.50 and purging with air which led to the formation of voluminous precipitates of ferric hydroxides with orange colour. The pulp was injected into the fixed-bed columns upward by a peristaltic pump, Ismatec, at flow rates of 0.096, 0.144, or 0.192 L/h, respectively. The temperature during the experiments was constant (25°C). The effluents from each fixed-bed column were collected separately and stored in a refrigerator until the chemical analysis. pH, iron and copper concentration were parameters used to characterise the columns' effluents hourly.

Fig. 1. Scheme of the experimental set-up used in the study

The fixed-bed columns were disassembled at the end of the experiment, and the ion exchange resin from each column was removed and mixed separately. 80 g/L H_2SO_4 (ratio aqueous: resin=2.5:1, at 30°C, and agitation of 300 rpm) in a batch regime extracted a sample from each column with a weight of 10 g. The resin's equilibrium amount of copper and iron was calculated from their solution concentrations. To determine the copper concentration in samples the copper ammonia method was used. The iron content (total and ferric state) was determined by its selective complexation with 5-sulphosalicylic acid at acidic and alkaline pH (Karamanev et al., 2002). The intensity of formed complexes was measured at the relevant wavelengths by the spectrophotometer MERCK SQ22.

Based on the collected data for each fixed-bed column, the relevant parameters - the total amount of solution passed through the column (V_{eff} , mL); a breakthrough point; a point of the column exhaustion, the total amount of iron entering the fixed-bed column until the moment of breakthrough point (m_{total} , mg), the total amount of adsorbed iron (q_{total} , mg), equilibrium amount of adsorbed iron (q_{eqFe} , mg/g ion exchange resin), the efficiency of iron removal (Y , %), equilibrium amount of adsorbed copper (q_{eqCu} , mg/g ion exchange resin), were evaluated using the respective equations (Malkoc et al., 2003; Sincero and Sincero, 2003; Aksu and Gönen, 2004; Ajmal et al., 2006):

$$V_{eff} = Q \cdot t_{total} \quad (1)$$

$$q_{total} = Q \cdot A / 1000 = [(Q/1000) \cdot \int_{t=0}^{t=t_{total}} (C_i - C_e) \cdot dt] \quad (2)$$

$$A = \sum [(t_{n+1} - t_n) \cdot [(C_{n+1}) - C_n]] / 2 \quad (3)$$

$$m_{total} = (C_i \cdot Q \cdot t_{total}) / 1000 \quad (4)$$

$$Y = (q_{total} / m_{total}) \cdot 100 \quad (5)$$

$$q_e = q_{total} / x \quad (6)$$

$$U_z = Z / t_z \quad (7)$$

$$C_{eq} = (m_{total} - q_{total}) / V_{eff} \quad (8)$$

where: C_e – iron content in effluents, mg/L; C_i – iron content in the inlet solution, mg/L; t_{total} – total flow time (h); Q – volumetric flow rate (mL/h); A – area under the integrated plot of adsorbed iron concentration versus flow time, cm^2 ; q_e – equilibrium iron adsorbed (mg/g); x – a unit mass of ion exchange resin LEWATIT MonoPlus TP 207 in the column; U_z – a rate of the saturation movement in the fixed bed-column, cm/h; t_z – time for the adsorption zone movement in the fixed bed-column, h.

The effect of the applied flow rate and the volume solutions injected into the columns on the iron adsorption by ion exchange resin LEWATIT MonoPlus TP 207 was studied by the breakthrough curves construction (function C_e / C_i of time).

Kinetic studies for evaluation of the iron breakthrough curves in fixed-bed columns

Bohart-Adams (Bohart and Adams, 1920; Qureshi et al., 2011), Thomas (Thomas, 1944), Yoon-Nelson (Yoon and Nelson, 1984), and Clark (Clark, 1987) models were used for kinetic studies of the iron adsorption on LEWATIT resin in a fixed-bed column. According to the Bohart-Adams model, the following equation describes the iron content in effluents of a fixed-bed column:

$$\ln (C_e / C_i) = [(-k_{BA} \cdot N_0 \cdot Z) / v] + (k_{BA} \cdot C_i \cdot t) \quad (9)$$

where k_{BA} is the Bohart-Adams rate constant [$L / (mg \cdot min)$], N_0 is the saturation concentration (mg/L), v is the linear velocity of AMD injection to a fixed-bed column (cm/min), Z is the bed depth (cm). The k_{BA} and N_0 were determined from the intercept and slope of the linear plot of $\ln (C_e / C_i)$ against time (t), respectively.

The Thomas model is given in linear form by the following expression:

$$\ln (C_i / C_e - 1) = [(k_{Th} \cdot q_{max} \cdot m) / Q] - (k_{Th} \cdot C_i \cdot t) \quad (10)$$

where k_{Th} is the Thomas rate constant [$L / (mg \cdot min)$], q_{max} is the maximum iron (mg/g), and m is the mass of sorbent resin in a fixed-bed column (g), Q is the volumetric flowrate of AMD (L/min). The parameters k_{Th} and q_{max} were determined from the intercept and slope of the linear plot of $\ln (C_i / C_e - 1)$ against time (t), respectively.

The Yoon-Nelson model is given in a linear form by the expression:

$$\ln [C_e / (C_i - C_e)] = (k_{YN} \cdot t) - (\tau \cdot k_{YN}) \quad (11)$$

where k_{YN} is the Yoon-Nelson rate constant (min^{-1}), τ is the time required for 50 % iron breakthrough (min). The parameters τ and k_{YN} were determined from the intercept and slope of the linear plot of $\ln [C_e / (C_i - C_e)]$ against time (t), respectively.

The Clark model is given in a linear form by the expression:

$$\ln [(C_i / C_e)^{n-1} - 1] = \ln A - r \cdot T \quad (12)$$

where n is the Freundlich constant determined experimentally

in a batch regime, r is the Clark rate constant (min^{-1}), and A is the Clark model constant. The parameters r and A were determined from the intercept and slope of the linear plot of $\ln [(C_e / C_i)^{n-1}]$ against time (t), respectively. The values of saturation concentration, N_0 and q_{\max} were calculated according to Rocha et al. (2015):

$$N_0 = C_i \cdot \ln A / Z \cdot r \quad (13)$$

$$q_{\max} = N_0 \cdot BH \quad (14)$$

where BH is the Bed volume/height of the adsorption zone in the fixed-bed column, cm^3/cm .

The regression coefficient (R^2) was used to evaluate the fitting of the experimental data to the linearised forms of the applied models.

Table 1. Characteristics of the fixed bed-columns experiment about the effect of flow rate on the Fe^{3+} adsorption on ion-exchange resin LEWATIT MonoPlus TP 207

Index	Applied bed volume per hour		
	2.0	3.0	4.0
Bed volume of the fixed-bed column, cm^3	48		
Bed height in the fixed-bed column, Z , cm	9.6		
Bed volume/height of adsorption zone, BH , cm^3/cm	5		
Mass of the resin in the column, m , g	62.3		
Fe in AMD, C_i , mg/L	3345		
Flow rate, L/h	0.096	0.144	0.192
The linear velocity of the solution, v , cm/min	0.166	0.249	0.333

Results and discussion

The volume of acid mine drainage generated at the mine sites varies quite a lot seasonally. The highest volume of mining effluents is detected in spring and autumn when the maximum annual precipitation is, opposite to summer when the minimum is. Therefore, the volume of generated acid mine drainage from mines had an opposite effect on the concentration of iron and non-ferrous metals being measured (Groudev et al., 2008). For that reason, the value of flow rate applied during the treatment of acid mine drainage, both by active and passive technologies, had a significant effect on the process efficiency. Three different flow rates of acid mine drainage with constant composition were applied to the fixed-bed columns to reveal that effect. The bed volume (BV) value determined the actual values of flow rates to the fixed-bed columns used in that study. The bed volume presents the total volume of pores between the resin beads, and its values in all columns were 48 mL (Table 1). The studied flow rates were 2.0, 3.0, and 4.0 BV, corresponding to 0.096, 0.144, and 0.192 L/h of acid mine drainage applied to the fixed-bed columns. The previous study (Georgiev et al., 2021) showed that the resin adsorbed the ferric iron preferentially when preliminary neutralised acid mine drainage to a pH of 3.50 is used. It enhanced ferrous to ferric iron oxidation in the presence of H_2O_2 and an excess of oxygen by air purging and iron hydrolysis and precipitation to goethite. The acid mine

drainage treated in that way was delivered to the fixed-bed columns upward. As a result, the solution filled up completely the column's bed volume, and cations took part in the ion-exchange processes with the protonated surface of the resin. As a result, the excess protons were transferred from the resin surface to the solution. Goethite dissolution was enhanced, ferric iron release to solutions, and its sorption on the resin surface. For that reason, apart from the iron and copper concentrations, the pH of effluents from each column was measured regularly (Table 2). The results revealed that the amount of ferric iron adsorbed on the resin surface was higher, while the pH of the columns effluents was lower. For example, pH and ferric iron concentrations in effluents at 2 hours since the start of the experiment were 1.23 and 141.6 mg/L, respectively, when the applied flow rate was 2 BV. However, when the applied flow rate was 4.0 BV, the iron sorption

Table 2. Characteristics of the fixed bed columns effluents depending on the applied flow rate

Index	Applied flow rate, BV/h		
	2.0	3.0	4.0
<i>4 BV passed through the column</i>			
Reached at time, hour	2.0	1.3	1.0
pH	1.23	1.38	1.47
Fe, mg/L	141.6	233.5	863.5
Cu, mg/L	12.6	23.4	38.2
<i>8 BV passed through the column</i>			
Reached at time, hour	4.0	2.6	2.0
pH	1.67	1.51	1.52
Fe, mg/L	2710	1812.6	2226
Cu, mg/L	176.4	171.4	165.6
<i>12 BV passed through the column</i>			
Reached at time, hour	6.0	4.0	3.0
pH	1.89	1.61	1.55
Fe, mg/L	3345	3345	3120
Cu, mg/L	164.3	160.8	157.6

Fig. 2. Breakthrough curves for Fe^{3+} adsorption on ion-exchange resin LEWATIT MonoPlus TP 207 at the studied flow rate

was carried out at a lower rate, and for that reason, pH and ferric iron concentration in the effluents increased to 1.47 and 863.5 mg/L, respectively, due to the shorter period of operation of that column. The longer the fixed-bed column operated at the relevant flow rate, pH and ferric concentration of effluents steadily increased due to gradual saturation of the resin's sorption capacity. Figure 2 depicts the gradual changes in iron concentration in the columns effluents depending on the applied flow rate. The total volume of solution delivered to the fixed bed columns until approximately 100 % iron breakthrough

at 2.0, 3.0, and 4.0 BV were at 0.384, 0.576, and 0.768 L, respectively (Table 3). After the end of each fixed-bed column's operation, the experiments showed that equilibrium iron content on the resin (q_{eqFe}) gradually decreased from 15.0 mg/g to 13.3 when the flow rate increased from 2.0 to 4.0 BV (Table 3). In the same order, the efficiency of iron sorption gradually decreased from 72.7% to 32.4% when the relevant volume of acid mine water passed through the fixed-bed columns. The lower values of equilibrium iron content on the resin was reported by other authors in the experiments when the inlet iron concentration to the fixed-bed columns decreased significantly (Millar et al., 2015; Victor-Ortega et al., 2016). The higher flow rates also had a negative effect on the values of the equilibrium content of copper on the resin (q_{eqCu}) and the ratio between equilibrium iron to copper content (q_{eqFe} / q_{eqCu}). Therefore, some limitations could arise in applying iron oxides produced during the further processing of the iron-loaded ion exchange resin (Georgiev et al., 2020).

Table 3. Parameters characterising the ferric iron adsorption on the ion-exchange resin LEWATIT MonoPlus TP 207 in a fixed bed-column

Index	Applied flow rate, BV/ h		
	2.0	3.0	4.0
Amount of solution passed through the column, V_{eff} , L	0.384	0.576	0.768
The total amount of ferric iron delivered to the fixed-bed column, m_{total} , mg	1285	1927	2569
The total amount of adsorbed iron, q_{total} , mg	934.5	913.1	831.9
The efficiency of the ferric iron adsorption, Y , %	72.7	47.4	32.4
Equilibrium amount of adsorbed iron, q_{eqFe} , mg/g	15.0	14.6	13.3
Equilibrium amount of adsorbed copper, q_{eqCu} , mg/g	0.47	0.51	0.56
Time of 50 % iron breakthrough concentration, hours	3.5	2.5	1.75
The ratio of q_{eqFe} / q_{eqCu}	31.9	28.7	23.8

Fig. 3. Bohart-Adams model for the Fe^{3+} adsorption on the ion-exchange resin LEWATIT MonoPlus TP 207 at the studied flow rate

The sorption processes carried out in fixed-bed columns are described by different mathematical models (Kundu and Gupta, 2005). These models are organised on the fraction of sorption capacity remaining free, model type followed during the adsorbate sorption, or the order of equation rate. For that reason, there is no universal model applicable for modelling

the sorption regardless of the type of studied adsorbate or used adsorbent.

The Bohart-Adams model is based on the surface reaction theory, according to which the rate of adsorption is proportional to the fraction of free adsorption capacity that still exists on the adsorbent surface (Bohart and Adams, 1920). That model was used to assess adsorbate removal by ion-exchange resins (Al-Sheikh et al., 2020). The results about the iron adsorption on the resin showed that the values of the linear velocity of solution through the fixed bed column, which was dependent on the applied flow rate, had a significant effect on the values of the Bohart-Adams rate constant (k_{BA}) and the saturation concentration (N_0), respectively (Table 4). For example, when the flow rate changed from 2.0 to 4.0 BV, the values of N_0 steadily increased and reached 18677 mg/ L at the highest applied flow rate. Meantime, the k_{BA} values decreased due to the higher linear solution's velocity passing through the resin bed in the column and the lower contact time for the ferric iron adsorption. For that reason, 13.3 mg Fe/g resin was the lowest value of the equilibrium iron content (q_{eq}) among the tested flow rates, determined experimentally at the study's end (Table 3). However, experimental fixed bed-column results fit well with the Bohart-Adams model when more than 50 % of binding sites of adsorbents are still unoccupied (Figure 3). For that reason, the Bohart-Adams model was not suitable for modelling iron adsorption from mining effluents, mainly when the fixed-bed column operates at higher flow rates.

Previous batch experiments revealed that ferric iron adsorption on LEWATIT resin followed second-order kinetics (Georgiev et al., 2021). The Thomas model follows the same kinetics, and it was included in the assessing tool for evaluating the experimental data for that reason (Thomas, 1944). The main advantage of the Thomas model is the determination of the maximum adsorbate content (q_{max}) retained on the adsorbent surface in a dynamic regime of operation.

Fig. 4. Thomas model for Fe^{3+} adsorption on the ion-exchange resin LEWATIT MonoPlus TP 207 at the studied flow rate

The values of q_{max} of iron adsorbed on the resin strongly depended on the applied flow rate of acid mine drainage to the column and Thomas rate constant (k_{Th}) (Table 4). For example, 2.0 BV used flow rate determined the highest values of q_{max} (18.2 mg/ g) on the ion exchange resin LEWATIT MonoPlus TP 207 (Table 4). However, the values of maximum iron content retained by the resin at all studied flow rates were higher both than the equilibrium iron content (q_e) determined experimentally at the end experiment (Table 3) and the maximum iron content (q_{max}) defined in a batch regime of operation (Georgiev et al., 2021). This discrepancy could be explained in two ways. Firstly, it is a well-known weakness that

the Thomas model overestimates the experimental values of the maximum adsorption capacity of adsorbents (Victor-Ortega et al., 2016; Negrea et al., 2020). Secondly, the acid mine drainage used in experiments contained 137 mg/L Cu²⁺ too, and despite ferric iron's preferential adsorption instead of copper (McKevitt and Dreisinger, 2009; Product Guide, 2021), some amount of it was also adsorbed (Table 3). As a result, it has a negative effect on the ferric iron content adsorbed by the ion exchange resin.

The main advantages of the Yoon-Nelson model (Yoon and Nelson, 1984) in comparison to the other models used in the study are fewer parameters needed for the model application and calculation of the time required for 50% of adsorbate breakthrough (τ). The data presented in Table 4 revealed that the values of τ had a tendency for steady decrease when higher flow rates of acid mine drainage to the fixed bed columns were applied.

Table 4. Ferric iron adsorption parameters on the ion-exchange resin LEWATIT MonoPlus TP 207 calculated by the applied models

Model	Flow rate, BV/h	Column adsorption parameters		R ²
Bohart-Adams		k_{BA} , L.mg ⁻¹ .min ⁻¹	N_0 , mg/L	
	2.0	$8.97 \cdot 10^{-6}$	13025	0.9923
	3.0	$7.47 \cdot 10^{-6}$	16145	0.9988
	4.0	$2.99 \cdot 10^{-6}$	18677	0.9318
Thomas		k_{Th} , (L.mg ⁻¹ .min ⁻¹)	q_{max} , mg/g	
	2.0	$1.14 \cdot 10^{-5}$	18.2	0.9936
	3.0	$1.23 \cdot 10^{-5}$	16.9	0.9671
	4.0	$9.27 \cdot 10^{-6}$	16.3	0.9990
Yoon-Nelson		k_{YN} , (min ⁻¹)	τ , (min)	
	2.0	0.038	211.8	0.9936
	3.0	0.043	153.5	0.9605
	4.0	0.031	97.7	0.9991
Clark		N_0 , mg/L	q_{max} , mg/g	
	2.0	199.9	16.1	0.9965
	3.0	189.4	15.2	0.9948
	4.0	170.7	13.7	0.9488

Fig. 5. Yoon-Nelson model for the Fe³⁺ adsorption on the ion-exchange resin LEWATIT MonoPlus TP 207 at the studied flow rate

Furthermore, the predicted times were very similar to the times determined during the monitoring of the fixed-bed column operation (Table 3). Figure 5 also shows that theoretical results fitted very well with the experimental ones depicted by the linear form of the model. For that reason, the Yoon-Nelson model could be used in other studies regarding raw components removal from laden leach solutions by ion-

exchange resins.

The Clark model was the last model applied to the experimental results. It is based on the assumption that adsorbate sorption follows the Freundlich isotherm (Clark, 1987). 1.909 was the value of the Freundlich constant n used to calculate the Clark parameters (r and $\ln A$) in the model. The values of both parameters decreased when higher flow rates were applied to the fixed-bed columns (data not shown). However, the values of correlation coefficients were higher than 0.99, which showed a good agreement between the model and the experimental results (Table 4, Figure 6).

Fig. 6. Clark model for the Fe³⁺ adsorption on the ion-exchange resin LEWATIT MonoPlus TP 207 at the studied flow rate

For that reason, considering the applied flow rates and the values of the Clark parameters calculated, the saturation concentration (N_0) and maximum adsorption capacity (q_{max}) described in the best way intimate mechanism of ferric adsorption on LEWATIT MonoPlus TP 207 ion-exchange resin. Furthermore, all calculated values for q_{max} were almost equal to the equilibrium iron content on the resin (q_e) determined experimentally at the end of the study (Table 3). For that reason, the Clark model could be used further in studies about non-ferrous metals, iron or other impurities removal from mining effluents by ion-exchange resins.

Conclusions

At constant experimental conditions (temperature, ferric iron concentration, and pH), the applied flow rate significantly affected equilibrium iron content, q_{eqFe} , on the ion-exchange resin LEWATIT MonoPlus TP 207. Its highest value was 15.0 mg/g when the applied flow rate to a fixed-bed column was 2 BV. However, when the fixed-bed column operated at higher flow rates, q_{eqFe} decreased gradually. It resulted from a lower percentage of iron removal, considering the total amount of iron delivered and worse ratio values between the equilibrium content of iron and copper on the resin.

The Yoon-Nelson and the Clark model better described ferric iron sorption on ion-exchange resin LEWATIT MonoPlus TP 207 than the other applied models (i.e. Bohart-Adams and Thomas models) and they could be used further in studies about the processing of rich-in-iron mining effluents with ion-exchange resins.

The Yoon-Nelson and the Clark rate constants of the models mentioned above are good tools to assess the effect of the flow rate on ferric iron sorption on the ion-exchange resin LEWATIT MonoPlus TP 207 in fixed-bed column studies.

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